

Tsukamoto, Kwah et al.

Supplemental dataset

Mass spectral analysis identifying high-confidence sites of phosphorylation sites in OOPS-1 and SPE-11, supported by multiple diagnostic b- and y-type fragment ions. These are reported in Fig. 7 in the main text.

Several additional medium- and low- confidence sites of potential phosphorylation were also detected but are not reported in Fig. 7

OOPS-1

Peptide tandem MS inspection for phosphorylation sites

- Annotate PTMs reported in Uniprot
- Show only PTMs
- Include PSMs that are Filtered Out

Coverage: 54.87%

Found Modifications:

- C** Carbamidomethyl (C)
- D** Deamidated (N,Q)
- G** Gln->pyro-Glu (N-term)
- O** Oxidation (M)
- P** Phospho (S,T)

Sequence		Modification List				
Position	Target	Modification	Classification	Highest Peptide Confidence	Sequence Motif	
311	N	Deamidated	Artefact	High	CCLKPCnSDAKTK	
318	M	Oxidation	Artefact	High	SDAKTKmRQISVQ	
320	Q	Gln->pyro-Glu	Artefact	High	AKTRMRqISVQVD	
324	Q	Deamidated	Artefact	High	MRQISVqVDHVTG	
341	Q	Gln->pyro-Glu	Artefact	High	SLPDVVRqHEGLVC	
347	C	Carbamidomethyl	Chemical derivative	High	QHEGLVcECLGDF	
349	C	Carbamidomethyl	Chemical derivative	High	EGLVCEcLGDFSL	
361	T	Phospho	Post-translational	High	LIRHRPtSVPVTKI	
362	S	Phospho	Post-translational	High	IRHRPTsVPVTKI	
439	Q	Deamidated	Artefact	High	LEKAGIqELEDGD	
459	S	Phospho	Post-translational	High	KYPKRsIVDGAS	
465	S	Phospho	Post-translational	High	SIVDGAsSETCED	
466	S	Phospho	Post-translational	High	IVDGASsETCEDT	
468	T	Phospho	Post-translational	High	DGASSEtCEDTQS	
469	C	Carbamidomethyl	Chemical derivative	High	GASSEtCEDTQSV	
473	Q	Deamidated	Artefact	High	ETCEDTqSVGSSE	
474	S	Phospho	Post-translational	High	TCEDTQsVGSSES	
477	S	Phospho	Post-translational	High	DTQSVGsSESSEp	
478	S	Phospho	Post-translational	High	TQSVGSsESSEPR	
480	S	Phospho	Post-translational	High	SVGSSEsSEPRSP	
481	S	Phospho	Post-translational	High	VGSSESsEPRSPe	
510	S	Phospho	Post-translational	High	SDSESSsEDEKEN	
516	N	Deamidated	Artefact	High	SEDEKENmKSSIK	
517	M	Oxidation	Artefact	High	EDEKENmKSSIKe	

Experiment VII (lab code 18902)

RLSSGDLNVIR (S108)

High confidence level

OOPS-1

Diagnostic fragment ions detected

Experiment V (lab code 18850)

LSsGDLNVIR (S109)

High confidence level

OOPS-1

Diagnostic fragment ions detected

Experiment VII (lab code 18902)

RLSSGDLNVIR (S108, S109)

High confidence level

OOPS-1

Diagnostic fragment ions detected

Experiment VI (lab code 18879) RMtEEIDFDLK (T119) High confidence level

OOPS-1

Diagnostic fragment ions detected

Experiment V (lab code 18850)

HRP^tSVPVTK (T361)

High confidence level

OOPS-1

Diagnostic fragment ions detected

Experiment V (lab code 18850)

HRPT_sVPVTK (S362)

High confidence level

OOPS-1

Diagnostic fragment ions detected with low intensity

Experiment V (lab code 18850)

SIVDGASSETcEDTQSVGsSESSEPR (S477)

High confidence level

OOPS-1

Diagnostic fragment ions detected

Experiment V (lab code 18850)

SIVDGASSETcEDTQSVGSSE_sSEPR (S480)

High confidence level

OOPS-1

Diagnostic fragment ions detected

Experiment VI (lab code 18879)

SIVDGASSETcEDTQSVGSSESsEPR (S481)

High confidence level

OOPS-1

Diagnostic fragment ions detected

Experiment VI (lab code 18879)

SIVDGASSETcEDTQSVGSsEsSEPR (S478, S480)

High confidence level

OOPS-1

Diagnostic fragment ions detected

Experiment V (lab code 18850)

KR^sIVDGASSETcEDTqSVGSSSESSEPR (S459)

Medium confidence level

OOPS-1

Diagnostic fragment ions detected with low intensity, some indistinguishable from other fragment ions of same m/z

Experiment V (code 18850)

KRSIVDGAS_sETcEDTqSVGSSSESSEPR (S466)

Medium confidence level

OOPS-1

Diagnostic fragment ions detected with low intensity, some indistinguishable from other fragment ions of same m/z

Experiment V (lab code 18850)

SIVDGASSETcEDTQSVGS_sESSEPR (S478)

Medium confidence level

OOPS-1

Diagnostic fragment ion 871 *m/z* in the noise; cannot discern between S478 and S477 localization; no supporting b ions

Experiment V (18850)

KRSIVDGAS_sETcEDTq_sVGSSESSEPR (S466, S474)

Low confidence level

OOPS-1

Diagnostic fragment ions detected with low intensity, some indistinguishable from other fragment ions of same m/z

Experiment V (lab code 18850)

SIVDGASSETcEDTQSVGSSES_sEPR (S481)

Low confidence level

OOPS-1

Diagnostic fragment ions in the noise

Experiment V (lab code 18850)

SIVDGASSETcEDTQSVGSSE^{ss}EPR (S480, S481)

Low confidence level

OOPS-1

Diagnostic fragment ions in the noise

Experiment V (lab code 18850)

SIVDGASSETcEDTQSVGSSSESsEPR (T468, S481)

Low confidence level

OOPS-1

Diagnostic fragment ions in the noise

SPE-11

Peptide tandem MS inspection for phosphorylation sites

Spermatocyte protein spe-11 OS=Caenorhabditis elegans OX=6239 GN=spe-11 PE=2 SV=1

- Annotate PTMs reported in Uniprot
- Show only PTMs
- Include PSMs that are Filtered Out

Coverage: **61.20%**

Found Modifications:

- C** Carbamidomethyl (C)
- D** Deamidated (N,Q)
- O** Oxidation (M)
- P** Phospho (S,Y)

Sequence		Modification List				
Position	Target	Modification	Classification	Highest Peptide Confidence	Sequence Motif	
1	M	Oxidation	Artefact	High	mSDEEID	
13	N	Deamidated	Artefact	High	DISTALnKTTTPK	
14	N	Deamidated	Artefact	High	ISTALNnKTTTPKK	
22	S	Phospho	Post-translational	High	TTPKKKsLKRNSN	
26	N	Deamidated	Artefact	High	KKSLKRnSNSQEG	
27	S	Phospho	Post-translational	High	KSLKRnSNSQEGY	
28	N	Deamidated	Artefact	High	SLKRNSnSQEGYE	
29	S	Phospho	Post-translational	High	LKRNSnSQEGYES	
30	Q	Deamidated	Artefact	High	KRNSNSqEGYESP	
33	Y	Phospho	Post-translational	High	SNSQEGyESPEER	
35	S	Phospho	Post-translational	High	SQEGYEsPEEREI	
54	M	Oxidation	Artefact	High	GAIGTPmAKSDNA	
88	M	Oxidation	Artefact	High	LRSKWdmTQGHLP	
117	M	Oxidation	Artefact	High	YNSKARmDILDGL	
133	C	Carbamidomethyl	Chemical derivative	High	NEGFFNcGKGAM	
164	M	Oxidation	Artefact	High	ATVETAmKKAGNP	
169	N	Deamidated	Artefact	High	AMKKAGnPTMEQM	
172	M	Oxidation	Artefact	High	KAGNPmEQMmTD	
174	Q	Deamidated	Artefact	High	GNPTMEqMmTDDL	
175	M	Oxidation	Artefact	High	NPTMEQmTDDL	
176	M	Oxidation	Artefact	High	PTMEQmTDDLDE	
209	M	Oxidation	Artefact	High	RAYDAAmDEREDD	
260	N	Deamidated	Artefact	High	KVTHKFnAYQLDL	
263	Q	Deamidated	Artefact	High	HKFNAYqLDLKL	
268	C	Carbamidomethyl	Chemical derivative	High	YQLDLKcLDEDAF	
276	N	Deamidated	Artefact	High	DEDAFSnKKSLKS	

[Partial list, from 18850]

Experiment VI (lab code 18879) MSDEEIDISTALNNKTPK (S2) High confidence level

SPE-11

Diagnostic fragment ions detected (y-1 to y-14 support no phos from C-term)

Experiment VI (lab code 18879) MSDEEIDISTALNNK^tPK (T17) High confidence level

SPE-11

Diagnostic fragment ions detected

Experiment VI (lab code 18879)

RN_SNSQEGYESPEER (S27)

High confidence level

SPE-11

Diagnostic fragment ions detected

Experiment IV (lab code 18822) NSNSQEGYESPEER (S29) High confidence level

SPE-11

Diagnostic fragment ions detected

Experiment VII (lab code 18902)

RN_SN_SQEGYESPEER (S27, S29)

High confidence level

SPE-11

Diagnostic fragment ions detected

Experiment VI (lab code 18879)

RNSNSQEGYE_sPEER (S35)

High confidence level

SPE-11

Diagnostic fragment ions detected

Experiment V (lab code 18850) RNSNsQEGYEsPEER (S29, S35) High confidence level

SPE-11

Diagnostic fragment ions detected

Experiment V (lab code 18850)

RN_sN_sQEGYE_sPEER (S27, S29, S35)

High confidence level

SPE-11

Diagnostic fragment ions detected

Experiment VII (lab code 18902)

AGNPtMEQMMTDDLDEDEARAEAEWER (T171)

High confidence level

SPE-11

Diagnostic fragment ions detected

Experiment VI (lab code 18879) NSNSQEG^yESPEEREIVPSVFGAIGTPMAK (Y33) Medium confidence level

SPE-11

Diagnostic fragment ions detected near the noise; site localization not clearly defined

Experiment V (lab code 18850)

SLKRNSNSQEGYESPEER (S22)

Low confidence level

SPE-11

Diagnostic fragment ions in the noise

Experiment VII (lab code 18902)

RNSNSQEG^yESPEER (Y33, S35)

Low confidence level

SPE-11

Diagnostic fragment ions in the noise